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Comic Books, Watergate and the Origin of the 1970s American Malaise.

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Introduction

It is axiomatic that the mere existence of comic book superheroes indicates a distrust in the ability of political systems to guarantee law, order, justice, or some such combination otherwise why would superheroes exist or be tolerated? The existence of comic book superheroes relies then on a premise that some part of the social contract is broken and so people must rely on extra-legal forces for protection from threats to their well-being. The concept is such a staple of comics that explorations of what would happen to superheroes if politicians exerted the authority of government, such as *Watchmen* (1986) and Marvel's crossover series *Civil War* (2006-2007) are seen as radical innovations on the form. But have superheroes always represented disquiet with existing systems and to what extent? And do they reflect, as journalistic doyen Russell Baker recently put it, "the traditional American distrust of 'politics'" (Baker 2013, 6). This article examines the transformation of politicians' representation in comic books in the mid-1970s. The events surrounding the Watergate burglary, and its corroding influence on American politics, impacted comic book views of politics and politicians. Most importantly it led to a generalized disdain for politicians, and hence politics, that set the scene for comics like *Watchmen*.

Background: Pre-Watergate

I argued elsewhere that the early Superman engaged in extra-legal activities to affect reform (Gordon 1998). But Superman's activities, while outside the letter of the law, did not represent a radical critique of politics. Indeed in the first Superman story *Action Comics #1* in 1938 Superman rushes to a governor mansion and breaks down the door, laughs as the Governor takes a shot at him, and then shows the Governor evidence that an innocent man is about to be executed (Siegel and Shuster 1938). So for Superman, who to be sure at this stage was not as powerful as later, but powerful

enough, the solution to the problem is to go to the Governor's mansion to plea a case rather than simply break the innocent man out of jail. The problem here is not that the system is broken, but rather that it has not worked so well and requires Superman's intervention to ensure justice is done.

From their origins comic book superheroes had a complex relationship with politics and power and that this was not a singular experience for all superheroes. But on the whole comic book superheroes worked within a recognizable frame in which, despite their extraordinary powers, superheroes accepted the validity and worth of the American political system. The origin of comic book superheroes in the late 1930s, in the midst of an expansion of Federal government power, and at a time when the President Franklin Roosevelt enjoyed immense popular support, might explain the popularity of comic book superheroes in this period. Roosevelt personified the immense power the Federal Government mobilized during the Depression and although it is a stretch to see him as a superhero his publicity machine created an image of an extraordinary person making a significant difference to the quality of people's lives (McElvaine 1983). Moreover as Gordon argues America's entry into World War II tied comic books to American values expressed broadly as the American Way (Gordon 1998). From 1938 until the 1970s this relationship remained much the same. To be sure various events like the anti-comic book campaign of the 1950s, and the industry's response to it, shaped some of the characterization of politicians, or more correctly the absence of such representations, in the pages of superhero comic books. But on the whole there was no major shift in the perception of politicians and politics until the late 1960s and early 1970s.

Tracing the unraveling of this view of politics and politicians in the pages of comic books is no simple matter. In the early 1960s when Stan Lee and others revitalized superhero comic books they often used the Cold War and the Vietnam War as plot devices. The Fantastic Four derived their powers from exposure to cosmic rays after Reed Richards steals a rocket ship, which he had been working on for the government, and takes off to space. The sole purpose for this venture is as Sue Storm explains is to prevent "the commies" beating Americans to space (*Fantastic Four* #1 1961). Iron Man originally created his suit to escape communists in Vietnam (*Tales of Suspense* #39 1963).

Robert Genter argues that Tony Stark/Iron Man represents an attempt by an individual to reclaim autonomy from corporations and the sort of group research projects common to large-scale scientific enquiry (Genter 2007). It is easy enough to see the origins of the Fantastic Four in similar circumstances with Reed Richards becoming frustrated at the level of government control of his work. Marvel's comics showed some of the fraying around the general post war consumerist society. That is to say there were tensions in American society and these in part drew on the general distrust of politics and the scale of government. Until about 1968 or so Marvel's heroes operated in a strictly delineated Cold War environment. But as the American War in Vietnam faced more and more opposition at home attitudes changed in comic books. Even so outright criticism of politicians was not something that typically appeared in comics until the 1970s.

Watergate and Captain America

Although American involvement in Vietnam wound down after the January 1973 Paris Peace Accord the Watergate scandal began unfurling in March 1973 further damaging the political fabric of America. In 1974 as Watergate reached its zenith Captain America struggled with the issue of politicians and his status as an American symbol. In a concise sequence in the August 1974 issue of *Captain America* writer Steve Englehart has the Captain note that "the government created me in 1941 -- created me to act as their agent in protecting our country" and that "I always tried to serve my country well – and now I find that the government was serving itself" (*Captain America and the Falcon* #176, 1974, 31). Despite pleas that America was more than the odd bad politician Captain America decided to call it a day. But in doing so he separated his actions of serving his country from the actions of the government serving itself and so made a distinction between the country and politicians who formed the government. Although Captain America abandoned his identity his alter ego Steve Rogers could not stay away from crime fighting and with a new costume and identity as Nomad continued as a superhero. Eventually seven months later in the March 1975 issue, after a reflective internal monologue at the Lincoln Memorial and an obligatory action sequence, Captain America returns reborn anew with a faith in the American dream rather than it in America per se. He declares "there has to be somebody who'll fight for the dream, always against any foe" (*Captain America and the Falcon* #183, 1975, 31). The any foe is a clear reference to politicians.

Such comics show the shifting attitudes to politics in 1960s comic books from outright support of the Vietnam War to disquiet with the political system. Even if the writers of

Captain America sought to make him symbolic of the American Dream rather than the country the only way they could do so was to dissociate him from the government and politicians. And indeed as writer Steve Englehart noted in issue #173 he had plotted the story in late 1972 well before Watergate reached public attention (*Captain America and the Falcon* #173, 1974, 19). Jason Dittmer, a human geographer, has discussed Captain America's role as an embodiment of the American Dream, often as he points out, as a counterpoint to the American government as part of a longer study (Dittmer 2013). This was not the last of Captain America's contretemps with the government over ideals. But it was the first and it marked a turning point for many comic book superheroes. In the pages of other comic books this disquiet expressed by Captain America began to grow into something more fundamental that laid the basis for a later distrust of politics and politicians to the point that the base Senator became a fixture of superhero films. The clearest example of this shifting attitude occurred in the comic book *Amazing Adventures*.

War of the Worlds: Killraven

In May 1973 issue 18 of *Amazing Adventures* contained the first story in a new series based on H. G. Well's *War of the Worlds* (*Amazing Adventures* #18 1973). The conceit of the story was that having failed in their attempt at conquest in 1901, due to the lack of immunity to human diseases, the Martians returned in 2001 armed with a general immunity, conquered earth and subjugated humanity. Killraven, the feature character, acquired his name as a gladiator trained to fight for Martian amusement. In this tale the complicity of humans in helping Martians control and enslave other humans played a central part. The political order has failed and those that could, mainly scientists, put their skills at the service of the Martians. For several issues of the comic book in 1974 Killraven goes to Washington. The May 1974 issue gives something of the flavor of the times with Washington described as, "not hell but it comes as close to it" as one would want to get (*Amazing Adventures* #24, 1974, 1)

The issue has a series of counterpoints that emphasized the general despair with politicians. Killraven finds some abandoned tapes, which given the comic's publication date are a clear reference to the missing tapes from Richard Nixon's secret recordings, tapes that would have implicated him in the cover up of the Watergate burglary. Killraven comments that the tapes are "probably from a day when politicians had trust and faith in their fellows – and their fellows in them" (*Amazing Adventures* #24, 1974, 10/4). To emphasize this point in another panel Killraven stands before the Lincoln Monument statue and the two figures are equated although "separated by time and

reality ... it is hardly distinguishable where one ends and the other begins" (*Amazing Adventures* #24, 1974, 18/2).

In this manner politicians of the 1970s are judged against the standard of Lincoln and found wanting. The sentiments to be sure were those of the author but by this the seventh issue of *Killraven* three authors had lent their hand to the series and the concept had been that of series editor Roy Thomas. Furthermore as some indication at how wide this anti-politician sentiment was among comic book writers in the mid-1970s a September 1976 fill-in issue of *Killraven* by Bill Mantlo demonstrated much the same sentiment with a critique of a distorted American Dream (*Amazing Adventures* #38 1976). In an otherwise fairly standard story using a dream sequence to offer comic book readers a team-up of many of Marvel's most popular characters Mantlo offered a critique of American power, the concept of the American dream, and the notion of superheroes, or at least the ways in which power could be perverted by ill-conceived dreams. In a telling penultimate scene *Killraven* says he has had enough dreams and would rather not join the superheroes to "become just another myth." He resists the dream still when an amalgam of Captain America and Gerard Ford tries to persuade him to join. Finally *Killraven* confronts the being projecting the dreams, a former astronaut affected with a sleeping sickness whose dreams of his childhood heroes became real "but changed like a kind of hell [he'd] created." *Killraven* kills him to end the nightmare (*Amazing Adventures* #38, 1976, 30-31). The story reads like a criticism of Captain America's acceptance of the American Dream as something worth holding on to particularly with Mantlo's association of the Captain and Gerald Ford, who had pardoned Nixon for any offenses he committed or may have committed during his full term in office. In that pardon Ford referred to ending the "bad dreams" prolonging a closed chapter of American history (Ford).

Unfortunately the comic book title was cancelled with the following issue so what reaction there was to this dream episode is unknown since the letter pages comic books carried generally had a two to three issue lag. The earlier Washington trilogy of stories evoked only one printed response that took issue with mention of the Watergate Tapes. In September 1974 in response to a letter complaining about the use of the Watergate Tapes in the March 1974 issue the editors responded that the overwhelming reaction of readers had been positive and that the use of the tapes had been ironic, which according to the editors the majority of letter writers had understood. The irony the Marvel editors raise seems to be *Killraven* referring to the tapes coming from a time when politicians must have been respected. This is a form of dramatic irony with the

readers of the comic book knowing the opposite to be true. It seems disingenuous for the editors to use the excuse of "irony" to counter the argument of letter writers who suggested that, if Marvel in trying to make stories "relevant to the times" decided to "harp on issues that are somewhat controversial," they would lose their audience who sought escapism (*Amazing Adventures* #26 1974). To be sure the letter writers had a conservative bent given that without seeing the story that the Watergate Tapes featured in they decided to complain about using such a narrative device, and they thought comic books should only be about escapism. But they did have a point. Using the Watergate tapes politicized the comic and lessened the escapism. But they missed a larger point. In *Killraven* as in most post-apocalyptic narratives there is a larger critique of politics. Politics and politicians have so completely failed that the governments and political systems have collapsed or not been successfully defended. So the escapism on offer here is a world without politics and politicians, which may either, be an unintended larger irony or a grander critique of American politics in the mid-1970s as leading America down a road to doom.

Slapstick Sarcasm as Political Critique: Howard the Duck

Irony involves a degree of sarcasm or ridicule. In *Howard the Duck*, another Marvel comic book from the mid-1970s, author Steve Gerber offered a highly sarcastic take on American society. Howard was a cigar chomping duck from another world. After appearing in other comics Howard received his own comic book in 1976. At first mostly a satire of horror tropes the comic book swiftly developed into a broad satire of American society. The comic book was popular enough to generate a truly awful film in 1986 that had little connection to the comic books satire. In the July 1976 issue a statement on the letters page announced a Howard the Duck campaign button (*Howard the Duck* #4 1976). Following that Gerber had Howard selected as the All Night Party's candidate for President in the December 1976 issue of the comic, which as with most comic books appeared on newsstands in October 1976, two months earlier than the cover date (*Howard the Duck* #7 1976). In the following issue political handlers attempt to make Howard a winning prospect by managing his image. What follows is a bitter and biting satire on politics in which Howard's refusal to be packaged and tendency to tell the truth mark him for assassination (*Howard the Duck* #8 1977). That Howard's truth telling was not that revelatory in any original sense about politics or the state of America is beside the point. Gerber explained the problems the United States faced in the words he had Howard speak: "You wonder why you've got violence? Why your young are either dissident, empty-headed, or drugged into a stupor? It's because you've fashioned an emotionally and intellectually sterile culture,

that's why!" (*Howard the Duck* #8, 1977, 26). The sterility of the culture was a common enough complaint about America from the 1950s on by critics as diverse as David Riesman, Paul Goodman, Vance Packard, C. Wright Mills, and William H. Whyte. Gerber to be sure was not offering analysis and solutions but producing entertainment. Gerber proffered an absurdist approach to "tumult and social trauma" and the resulting "mediocrity" of the presidential candidates by having a talking duck run for the office (*Howard the Duck* #4, 1976, 19). Eventual Howard's campaign comes undone in the comic book pages when a photo of him bathing with a female companion appears in the press. The photo turns out to be a forgery and that of course is Gerber's point that politics is about misinformation, dirty tricks, and media spin. And as a character says in the February 1977 issue "nobody cares" who won (*Howard the Duck* #9, 1977, 2/1). For Gerber too politics was not part of the solution, but rather part of a broader problem.

From Watergate to Comic Book Superhero films

The general sense of uneasiness in *Killraven* and *Howard the Duck* was common to many comic books in the 1970s, as Matthew Pustz has shown, and a constituent element in a sense of malaise within American culture and society (Pustz 2012). Pustz drawing on Jimmy Carter's Presidential address of July 15, 1979 lists a series of phenomena that contributed to this general anxiety: the assassinations of the 1960s, the Vietnam War, Watergate, and stagflation. Although Carter never used the word malaise in his address he did suggest that a deep seated problem existed in an upsurge of cynicism among Americans about, as a *New York Times* report put it, "the future of the country and their own personal lives" (Smith 1979). Carter told Americans that some of their problems were because they were spending too much and not saving as much as they should and that "too many of us now tend to worship self-indulgence" (Horowitz 2004). Carter's speech and his seeming inability to lead the nation both in domestic and international policies, especially the Iran hostage crisis, only compounded the sense of malaise.

In the year of Carter's speech *Superman* the movie, the first blockbuster based on a comic book superhero, grossed \$134 million in the American domestic market (Denison 2007; McAllister, Gordon, and Jancovich 2006). Perhaps some of the appeal of the movie was the message of uplift it offered a cynical America. *Superman* put that cynicism on display, but rejected it both directly in dialogue and indirectly through the good triumphing over evil plot. Nonetheless the film linked politics to corruption.

The film set a mood of cynicism through the scenes in the *Daily Planet* newsroom by evoking two other films; the genre humor and feel of Howard Hawks's 1940 movie *His Girl Friday* especially the fast cracking, make wise dialogue in an early scene in *Superman* when Clark first meets Lois Lane in Perry White's office, and the general *mise-en-scene* of the busy newspaper city room as depicted in the 1976 movie adaptation of Bob Woodward and Carl Bernstein's Watergate scandal account, *All the President's Men*, directed by Alan J. Pakula. The humor of *His Girl Friday* fit the general absurdist response to the perceived indifference of social institutions in the 1930s. Giving the *Daily Planet* on film the look and feel of the newsroom in *All the President's Men* neatly evoked the Watergate scandal. The *Daily Planet* is very much a character in the movie and the newspaper and the traditions of crusading newspaper reporters ties the 1978 *Superman* movie to the 1938 comic book. Director Richard Donner sets up this scenario in the movie's opening sequence. The movie opens with a cinema curtain parting, complete with a soundtrack incorporating the noises of a curtain being drawn. Then to the sound of film running through a projector the words: June, 1938, appear on the screen followed by the fade in of a comic book cover that reads *Action Comics* and which has an illustration of two rocket ships fleeing an exploding planet. A hand turns the page and a boy's voice says: "In the decade of the 1930s even the great city of Metropolis was not spared the ravages of the world wide depression. In the times of fear and confusion the job of informing the public was the responsibility of the *Daily Planet*, a great metropolitan newspaper, whose reputation for clarity and truth had become a symbol of hope for the city of Metropolis." The scene then dissolves from the comic book to a live scene of the *Daily Planet* building and the spinning globe on top and then pans to the night sky and stars and the opening credits roll as the camera sweeps through space over the stirring John Williams score (*Superman* 1978). In 1978 it may have been an easy connection for an audience to understand that the fear and confusion of the Depression was as much a threat to the USA as the Watergate shenanigans of President Nixon and to understand the *Daily Planet* as akin to *the Washington Post*. Elsewhere in the movie Perry White makes the link explicit when he says that he wishes the name of the yet unnamed Superman "to go with the *Daily Planet* like Bacon and Eggs, Franks and Beans, Death and Taxes, Politics and Corruption" (*Superman* 1978).

Although such cynicism is evoked throughout the movie Superman never expresses it himself. Indeed he stands firm against its expression. In a key scene in the movie where the audience and Lois learn much about Superman's powers and character through her interview with him she asks: "Why are you here; there must be a reason for

you to be here?” And Superman replies: “Yes I am here to fight for truth and justice, and the American way.” Lois laughs in reply and says: “you are going to end up fighting every elected official in this country.” Superman, or at least his scriptwriters, understood that if Americans felt that all their elected officials were corrupt, then they simply wanted to be told by someone that this was not the case and the nation still held out its promise to the world. As if to drive this point home the movie’s next scene showed Superman flying Lois around the Statue of Liberty in a long swooping shot the length of which forces the viewer to ponder the Statue and perhaps remember the inscription thereon and the accompanying ideology of America as a light on the hill to the rest of the world.

Just as Steve Englehart disassociated the American dream, and hence Captain America from politics, *Superman* the movie set Superman apart from politics. If politics and corruption went hand in hand then Superman who never lied rose above such tawdry matters and stood in contrast to such baseness. So while Donner’s *Superman* and its sequel, Richard Lester’s *Superman II* (1980), reaffirmed the goodness and greatness of America they did so in the context of politics being viewed as at best degraded. Since that time, and thanks to Watergate, the ignoble politician has become a-ready-made film shorthand for ascribing the virtue of a comic book superhero making the transition to film.

Conclusion

The relationship between politics and superheroes is perhaps blunter in films. But since the early to mid-1970s both film and comic book superheroes have on the whole had a disdain for politics and politicians. Expecting fictional superheroes to engage with the daily cut and thrust of politics is unrealistic if for no other reason than such heroes are commercial entities and need polysemic appeal. Rather superheroes stand for broad unifying symbolic concepts like the American Dream (Dittmer 2013) and the American Way (Gordon 2001). Such concepts, which to be sure are ideological, are broad enough to encompass many perspectives. The conduct of politics is in some ways a struggle to shape specific versions of these broad principles as policies that protect and enable the broader vision, albeit according to some particular perspective. Opposing viewpoints, and the resulting political contests about how best to enact principles, also begin to reveal and suggest the limits of those principles narrowing them from ideals and generalities to specifics. In highly politicized climates then creators of superhero entertainments like comic books and films need to find ways to maintain their unifying, and saleable, symbolic legitimacy. From the 1970s the creators of superhero

entertainments have tried to distinguish the virtuous superhero, symbolic of American values, from the corrupting exigencies of politics.

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